

REport Generation of pathology using Pan-Asia Giga-pixel WSIs (2025): Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

REport Generation of pathology using Pan-Asia Giga-pixel WSIs (2025)

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

REG2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Recent advances in vision-language foundation models have opened new possibilities in medical applications, particularly in image captioning, which generates textual descriptions from images. When applied to gigapixel-scale pathology images, this task demands advanced image analysis methods like slide-level feature extraction to process and interpret vast visual data. Automated pathology report generation, despite its complexities, has gained attention for its potential to address labor shortages, improve diagnostic accuracy, and enhance patient care. However, current evaluation methods relying on traditional NLP metrics such as BLEU, METEOR, and ROUGE are inadequate for the medical domain, where clinical relevance and content accuracy are paramount.

To address these limitations, this initiative focuses on: 1) evaluating report generation models with standardized datasets encompassing diverse pathological cases; 2) comparing generated reports with expert assessments to measure clinical alignment; 3) identifying and adopting evaluation metrics tailored to medical standards; and 4) exploring the integration of generated reports into diagnostic workflows, informed by clinical feedback.

Our ultimate goal is to enhance the practicality and reliability of pathology report generation models by ensuring they produce clinically meaningful and high-quality content. Furthermore, this initiative aims to address the limitations of current AI models in reflecting racial and ethnic diversity by utilizing a broader dataset that includes both Pan-Asia and European data. The challenge dataset comprises approximately 20,500 cases collected from six medical centers across five countries—Korea, Japan, India, Turkey, and Germany—contributing to the development of multicultural and multiethnic medical AI technologies.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Image captioning, Report generation, Multi-modal, Pan-Asia, Pathology, Whole-slide-image

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge is innovative in that it introduces a novel evaluation framework that reflects the clinical value of AI-driven pathology report generation. Traditional studies on automated pathology report generation have primarily relied on NLP metrics such as BLEU and ROUGE, which fail to adequately capture the unique requirements of the medical domain. To address this limitation, this challenge implements a multi-metric evaluation approach that more effectively assesses clinical accuracy and semantic relevance, ensuring that the generated reports are optimized for real-world clinical applicability.

Furthermore, this challenge represents one of the first large-scale benchmarks for pathology report generation that explicitly incorporates multicultural and multiethnic medical data, helping to overcome the Western-centric bias prevalent in existing research. The expanded dataset now includes both Pan-Asia and European pathology data. The 20,500 WSIs utilized in this challenge consist of pathology slide images and reports collected from six leading medical institutions across five countries—Korea, Japan, India, Turkey, and Germany. By integrating data from diverse racial and medical environments, this initiative facilitates the development of more generalizable, fair, and reliable AI models for pathology report generation.

Currently, 11,280 images have been collected from Korea University Medical Center, 2,001 images from Kameda, 334 images from Memorial Health Group, 2,000 images from AIIMS, 2,000 images from Tata Memorial Hospital, and 1,500 images from University Hospital Cologne. A total of 19,115 images have been secured so far, and the remaining data (1,385 images) is planned to be additionally collected by March 2025. Furthermore, all data will undergo expert pathological review to ensure rigorous quality management in accordance with the MICCAI 2025 timeline.

In conclusion, this challenge aims to advance the field by overcoming the limitations of conventional evaluation methods through a clinically driven assessment framework, while also establishing the first large-scale pathology report generation benchmark incorporating diverse pathology datasets panning Asia and Europe. Through these contributions, this challenge seeks to drive progress in pathology AI research and its real-world clinical adoption.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

This challenge aims to develop and evaluate AI models that automatically generate pathology reports by analyzing Whole Slide Images (WSIs).

Input: Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E;) stained pathology slide images (WSIs)

Output: Automatically generated pathology reports

Task Objectives:

- 1) Evaluate the performance of AI-based automated pathology report generation models.
- 2) Develop and apply medical domain-specific evaluation metrics that address the limitations of traditional NLP metrics.
- 3) Explore AI models capable of generating reports suitable for real-world clinical applications.
- 4) Develop models that generalize across multicultural and multiethnic medical environments.

Evaluation Metrics:

- 1) Textual similarity of reports (Word Score, ROUGE-L, BLEU-4)
- 2) Inclusion of key pathology terms (Keyword Score, Scispacy Jaccard)
- 3) Semantic accuracy and clinical relevance (Embedding Score, OpenBioLLM-Llama3-70B)
- 4) Multi-metric weighted evaluation approach (Weighted Score)

Application Scenarios:

The AI-based pathology report generation technology developed in this challenge can be applied in various clinical and research settings:

- 1) Supporting pathologists by enhancing efficiency and diagnostic accuracy
- 2) Integration with Clinical Decision Support (CDS) systems
- 3) Integration with medical AI systems and automated pathology analysis platforms
- 4) Application in multicultural and multiethnic medical environments
- 5) Establishing a benchmark for research and development

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS**Workshop**

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

The challenge is associated with MICCAI 2025 and will be part of a workshop focusing on AI-driven pathology report generation.

The workshop will explore AI-based pathology report generation, clinical NLP evaluation, and multimodal learning for WSIs, providing a platform for discussing state-of-the-art methodologies in this domain.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Approximately 5 months, from April 2025 to September 2025

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

This challenge spans approximately 5 months to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of AI models for pathology report generation. Unlike single-day competitions, this challenge requires:

- 1) Model Training and Optimization: Participants need sufficient time to develop, train, and refine their AI models on complex Whole Slide Image (WSI) datasets.
- 2) Multi-Phase Evaluation: The challenge includes a structured evaluation process, with distinct phases for training, testing, and submission.

3) Realistic Clinical Validation: AI models for medical applications must be rigorously assessed for clinical relevance and robustness, requiring an extended timeline for evaluation.

This extended duration allows participants to experiment with different approaches, improve their models based on validation feedback, and submit high-quality solutions that align with real-world medical applications.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

The field of clinical report generation has gained significant momentum worldwide. In 2024 alone, a Google Scholar search returned over 150 relevant research papers on this topic. That same year, we organized the REG2024 (Report Generation for Pathology using Giga-pixel Whole Slide Images in Bladder Tumor) local challenge in Korea (<https://www.medifonews.com/news/article.html?no=193784>), which attracted more than 30 participating teams.

Given the increasing global interest in clinical report generation, the availability of large-scale datasets, and the visibility of MICCAI, we anticipate that a global competition of this scale will attract at least 300 participating teams. This estimate is grounded in:

- The rising trend in published research, as evidenced by the 150+ papers in 2024,
- The substantial engagement observed in previous challenges (such as REG2024), and
- The reputation of MICCAI as a leading conference in the medical imaging community.

We have already reached out to multiple research groups worldwide, many of whom have expressed interest in participating. As the challenge gains further publicity through MICCAI channels, we expect the final number of participants may exceed our conservative estimate of 300.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, we plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results. Our goal is to prepare a high-quality manuscript detailing the challenge design, methods, and outcomes, and to submit it to Medical Image Analysis, a premier journal within the MICCAI community.

We have prior experience organizing and publishing the outcomes of similar challenges. For instance, following the LDCT-IQAC 2023 challenge (<https://ldctiqac2023.grand-challenge.org/>), we successfully published the results in Medical Image Analysis (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2024.103343>). Building on that experience, we are confident in our ability to coordinate a smooth publication process, ensuring wide dissemination of the challenge findings and meaningful engagement with the broader research community.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Since this challenge will be conducted entirely online, there are no specific on-site hardware requirements.

1. Platform: The challenge will be hosted on Grand Challenge (<https://grand-challenge.org/>), where participants will submit their results for evaluation.
2. Computing Requirements: Participants are expected to train their models using their own computational resources (e.g., GPUs, cloud computing). No centralized training infrastructure will be provided.
3. Evaluation Environment: All submissions will be evaluated in a standardized computing environment within the Grand Challenge platform to ensure fairness.
4. Technical Support: The organizing team will provide detailed documentation and FAQs to assist participants with submission and troubleshooting.

TASK 1: REport Generation of pathology using Pan-Asia Giga-pixel WSIs (2025)

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Recent advances in vision-language foundation models have opened new possibilities in medical applications, particularly in image captioning, which generates textual descriptions from images. When applied to gigapixel-scale pathology images, this task demands advanced image analysis methods like slide-level feature extraction to process and interpret vast visual data. Automated pathology report generation, despite its complexities, has gained attention for its potential to address labor shortages, improve diagnostic accuracy, and enhance patient care. However, current evaluation methods relying on traditional NLP metrics such as BLEU, METEOR, and ROUGE are inadequate for the medical domain, where clinical relevance and content accuracy are paramount.

To address these limitations, this initiative focuses on: 1) evaluating report generation models with standardized datasets encompassing diverse pathological cases; 2) comparing generated reports with expert assessments to measure clinical alignment; 3) identifying and adopting evaluation metrics tailored to medical standards; and 4) exploring the integration of generated reports into diagnostic workflows, informed by clinical feedback.

Our ultimate goal is to enhance the practicality and reliability of pathology report generation models by ensuring they produce clinically meaningful and high-quality content. Furthermore, this initiative aims to address the limitations of current AI models in reflecting racial and ethnic diversity by utilizing a broader dataset that includes both Pan-Asia and European data. The challenge dataset comprises approximately 20,500 cases collected from six medical centers across five countries—Korea, Japan, India, Turkey, and Germany—contributing to the development of multicultural and multiethnic medical AI technologies.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Image captioning, Report generation, Multi-modal, Pan-Asia, Pathology, Whole-slide-image

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

YuMi Lee* (Ewha Womans University, Korea),

Ha Rim Oh* (Korea University Anam Hospital, Korea),

Andrey Bychlov (Kameda Medical Center, Japan),

Junya Fukuoka (Kameda Medical Center, Japan),

Rajiv Kumar Kaushal (Tata Memorial Hospital, India),
Ayushi Sahay (Tata Memorial Hospital, India),
Rajni Yadav (All India Institute Of Medical Sciences Delhi, India),
Sulen Sarioglu (Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul, Turkey),
Serdar Balci (Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul, Turkey),
İlknur Türkmen (Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul, Turkey),
Yuri Tolkach (University Hospital Cologne, Germany),
Christian Harder (University Hospital Cologne, Germany),
Jang-Hwan Choi† (Ewha Womans University, Korea),
Sangeong Ahn† (Korea University Anam Hospital, Korea)

*These authors contributed equally

†Primary contacts

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

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Email id: vanitasahn@gmail.com

Jang-Hwan Choi (Department of Artificial Intelligence, Ewha Wmans University, Korea)

Email id: choij@ewha.ac.kr

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

<https://grand-challenge.org/>

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

We will create our own challenge website on the Grand Challenge platform, which will be made publicly available upon acceptance.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May not participate

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 5 winners will receive monetary awards and certificates. The total prize pool is expected to be approximately \$2,000. We are currently coordinating with sponsors to finalize the exact prize amounts, which will be confirmed upon the launch of the challenge website.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.
- A public leaderboard will provide live performance rankings throughout the challenge, while the final leaderboard, reflecting the official results, will be displayed on the Grand Challenge platform.
- The top-performing methods (top N) will be publicly announced during the MICCAI 2025 conference.
- All participants will be required to submit a technical abstract detailing their approach, including methodology, results, and key insights.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

We will write a journal paper presenting and discussing the results from the challenge to be submitted to an international journal. The challengers will be asked to participate to a special issue of a journal for presenting their approach.

Participant teams that have submitted valid methods and completed the technical paper at the end of challenge will be allowed to use their own performance scores for publication separately after the challenge (12 months embargo time will be imposed after the challenge day).

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

In order to ensure reproducibility, all participants must submit the following materials by email to the primary organizer:

1. A CSV file for the generated report. The exact format will be provided on the challenge platform.
2. A final report detailing the proposed method. This report should include the key contributions, the number of model parameters, as well as the results and their analysis. A Word template will be made available on the challenge platform.
3. A ZIP file containing the complete source code and the trained model parameters. The source code must include a requirements.txt file listing all packages and their corresponding version numbers.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants may upload and submit their generated reports in the provided CSV format for evaluation, with a maximum of five submissions allowed throughout the challenge. During each evaluation, performance will be assessed on the hidden validation set (Approximately 2,000 cases) using the grand-challenge.org platform, and team rankings will be updated in real-time on a live public leaderboard. To ensure fairness and reproducibility, all participants must submit not only their predicted results but also their source code and trained model weights. Additionally, the evaluation environment is standardized, with a clearly specified data provision method, baseline code, and recommended library versions, ensuring that all participants conduct their experiments under the same conditions. Only the final submission from each team will be evaluated on the hidden testing set (Approximately 2,000 cases) to determine the final ranking of the submitted algorithms.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

An estimated timetable is given below

Registration open: April 2025

Releasing training dataset: May 2025

Start of test phase: July 2025

End of test phase: August 2025

Methodology reports due: August 2025

Winner announced: September 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Medical Ethics Committee of Korea University Anam Hospital (Korea), Kameda Medical Center (Japan), and University Hospital Cologne (Germany) approved this challenge protocol. Other participating institutions, including Tata Memorial Hospital (India), All India Institute of Medical Sciences Delhi (India), and Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul (Turkey) are in the process of obtaining IRB approval for data collection. Updates regarding this process will be provided at a later stage.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation will be automatically performed in the challenge platform. Information about the evaluation formula and its algorithm will also be available on the platform.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

To evaluate and ensure the reproducibility of the submitted algorithms, participants will be required to provide their GitHub repositories containing the proposed methods along with their final submission. Consequently, all participants' code will be made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There are no conflicts of interest. The only sponsorship for the challenge will be in the form of award money, although the sponsors have not yet been finalized. Access to the test case WSIs and labels, both during and after the challenge, will be restricted exclusively to members of the organizing team.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis,Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval

- Segmentation

- Tracking

Image captioning

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of patients undergoing biopsy or small-sized tissue removal from multiple organs, including the lung, colon, breast, urinary bladder, stomach, uterine cervix, prostate, and others.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort would be acquired the same way as the target cohort.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Hematoxylin-eosin (HE) stained histopathology whole-slide images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

For each image in the training data, an anonymous case ID is provided, along with pathology report (including organ, main diagnosis, and required description based on CAP guideline). No pathology report will be provided for test data.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No further information given

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data consists of WSIs from the target cohort, obtained from the organizer center, with following 38 diagnostic categories across 7 organs:

- Lung (5): Adenocarcinoma, Squamous cell carcinoma, Small cell carcinoma, Necrotizing granulomatous

inflammation, Normal lung parenchyme

- Colon (10): Adenocarcinoma, Tubular adenoma with low grade dysplasia, Tubular adenoma with high grade dysplasia, Tubulovillous adenoma with low grade dysplasia, Tubulovillous adenoma with high grade dysplasia, Villous adenoma with low grade dysplasia, Villous adenoma with high grade dysplasia, Hyperplastic polyp, Serrated lesion, Normal
- Breast (5): Invasive ductal carcinoma, Invasive lobular carcinoma, Ductal carcinoma in situ, Fibroepithelial tumor, No evidence of tumor
- Urinary bladder (5): Invasive urothelial carcinoma with muscle proper invasion, Invasive urothelial carcinoma with subepithelial connective tissue invasion, Non-invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma, high grade, Non-invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma, low grade, Urothelial carcinoma in situ
- Stomach (5): Adenocarcinoma, Tubular adenoma with low grade dysplasia, Tubular adenoma with high grade dysplasia, MALToma, Normal
- Uterine cervix (6): LSIL, HSIL, Squamous cell carcinoma, Normal, Adenocarcinoma in situ, Adenocarcinoma
- Prostate (2): Acinar adenocarcinoma, normal

The data provided by Korea University Anam Hospital (Korea), Kameda Medical Center (Japan), and Tata Memorial Hospital (India) includes all the mentioned organs, whereas the data from other institutions does not include certain organs.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Algorithms should aim to generate comprehensive pathology reports directly from WSIs. The target of these algorithms includes accurately identifying and characterizing pathological features such as tumors, dysplastic lesions, or inflammatory processes across various organs (e.g., lung, colon, breast, urinary bladder) and translating these findings into structured diagnostic reports.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Word score(ROUGE-L, BLUE-4),Keyword score(Scispacy Jaccard),Embedding score

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Data would be collected from organizing centers and scanned using multiple scanners, including Aperio AT2, Leica GT450 scanner, and etc.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The slides were scanned at 20X or 40X magnification.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data would be acquired from six medical centers across Asia and Europe: Korea University Anam Hospital (Korea), Kameda Medical Center (Japan), Tata Memorial Hospital (India), All India Institute Of Medical Sciences Delhi (India), Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul (Turkey), and University Hospital Cologne (Germany). This expansion aims to enhance the generalizability of the developed algorithms by incorporating diverse pathology data beyond the Pan-Asia region, ensuring broader applicability in real-world clinical settings. Additional medical centers may be included to further improve dataset diversity.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

None

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

In the training and test data, a case refers to a single WSI corresponding to one subject. The training cases are accompanied by paired pathology reports, while the test cases are provided with only the WSI.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Total: approximately 20,500 cases

Training: approximately 15,000 cases (paired WSIs and pathology reports)

Validation: approximately 2,000 cases (paired WSIs and pathology reports)

Test: approximately 2,000 cases (WSIs only) + Additional European dataset: 1,500 cases (University Hospital Cologne, Germany, WSIs and pathology reports for generalization testing)

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The dataset will comprise 20,500 WSI-report pairs covering 38 disease types across 7 organs. To ensure balanced representation, 10% of each disease category will be included in the test set, resulting in 2,000 test samples. Consequently, 15,000 samples will be provided for training and 2,000 samples for validation and testing. Additionally, 1,500 cases from University Hospital Cologne (Germany) will be incorporated to enhance algorithm generalizability across diverse populations.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Distribution of classes follow an equal class distribution.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The dataset for this challenge will be entirely composed of newly acquired, unpublished Whole Slide Images (WSIs) collected from six medical centers across Asia and Europe: Korea University Anam Hospital (Korea), Kameda Medical Center (Japan), Tata Memorial Hospital (India), All India Institute Of Medical Sciences Delhi (India), Memorial Healthcare Group Istanbul (Turkey), and University Hospital Cologne (Germany). This expansion aims to improve algorithm generalization by incorporating diverse pathology data beyond the Pan-Asia region. Additional medical centers may be included to further enhance dataset diversity.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Pathologist from data-contributing centers provided the original pathology reports for each case.

All training and test case samples will be curated by expert pathologists at Korea University anam Hospital. No manual annotations are involved.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Not applicable.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The pathologist who participated in this study were subspecialized in gastrointestinal pathology (S.A.), pulmonary pathology (J.F.), uropathology (R.K.K), breast pathology (A.S.) and other pathology specialties, with on average 12 years of experience in subspecial pathology.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

During data curation, cases with a disagreements regarding the main diagnosis or grade were resolved through consensus with subspecialist pathologists from the Asian Society of Digital Pathology (ASDP) in each field (e.g., gastrointestinal, urology, pulmonary, breast). The consensus process involved multiple rounds to ensure accuracy

and reliability.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

De-identification and anonymization are applied to WSIs that are difficult to identify, and preprocessing ensures that only one tissue is used if multiple tissues are present in a single WSI.

For the training and validation cases, pathology report text files (.txt) corresponding to each WSI are provided in accordance with the CAP guidelines.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter-observer variability among expert pathologists may result in discrepancies in tumor classification and grading. The training and test cases were exclusively curated from cases where consensus among pathologists was achieved.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will use automatic evaluation metrics to assess the generated text by comparing it with the original pathology report. The metrics include ROUGE-L, BLEU-4, Scispacy Jaccard, and Embedding score, each capturing distinct aspects of text similarity and clinical relevance. A weighted sum of these metrics will be calculated to derive the overall performance score, which will be used to rank of the algorithms. Incorporating specific keyword and phrase analysis may introduce subjective elements; therefore, it will not be included in the evaluation.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

1. Word score: This metric evaluates the textual similarity between generated and ground-truth reports using Rouge-L [1] and BLEU4 [2] score.
2. Keyword Score: Assessed using Scispacy [3], this metric measures the overlap of key medical terms between the generated and ground-truth reports, ensuring domain-specific terminology alignment
3. Embedding score: Using OpenBioLLM-Llama3-70B [4], a fine-tuned variant of LLaMA-3-8B optimized for biomedical applications, this metric captures semantic similarity, focusing on the clinical relevance and conceptual alignment between the generated and ground-truth reports.

Conventional metrics, such as BLEU4 or Rouge-L, often fall short in evaluating the nuanced language and clinical depth required in pathology reports. While these metrics can quantify structural aspects, they fail to address the critical aspects of clinical relevance essential for real-world medical applications. To overcome these limitations, a weighted sum approach combining four metrics is proposed, enabling a more comprehensive evaluation of report quality:

$$\text{Ranking score} = 0.15 \cdot \text{ROUGE-L} + 0.15 \cdot \text{BLEU-4} + 0.3 \cdot \text{Scispacy Jaccard} + 0.4 \cdot \text{Embedding score}$$

[1] Lin, C. Y. (2004, July). Rouge: A package for automatic evaluation of summaries. In Text summarization branches out (pp. 74-81).

[2] Papineni, K., Roukos, S., Ward, T., & Zhu, W. J. (2002, July). Bleu: a method for automatic evaluation of machine translation. In Proceedings of the 40th annual meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (pp. 311-318).

[3] Neumann, M., King, D., Beltagy, I., & Ammar, W. (2019). ScispaCy: fast and robust models for biomedical natural language processing. arXiv preprint arXiv:1902.07669.

[4] Pal, M. S. A., & Sankarasubbu, M. (2024). OpenBioLLMs: Advancing open-source large language models for healthcare and life sciences. Retrieved from <https://huggingface.co/aaditya/OpenBioLLM-Llama3-70B>.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

For each test case, participants are required to provide a generated text, which will be compared to the original pathology reports. To compute the performance rank, we will calculate performance metrics as described in section 26 for each test case. The participants will then be ranked based on their average performance across all test cases. The final ranking will reflect the overall quality of the generated pathology reports.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

In this challenge, we allow missing predictions for certain test cases but apply a clear penalty mechanism to maintain fairness and encourage completeness. Specifically:

1. Scoring Mechanism

- Any test case with a missing prediction automatically receives a score of zero.
- Final performance metrics (e.g., BLEU, METEOR, clinical relevance metrics) are computed by averaging or combining scores from all test cases.
- As a result, the more missing predictions a submission has, the more its final score is directly penalized.

2. Rationale

- Rather than disqualifying submissions that have missing results, we aim to foster innovation by allowing different methods and approaches.
- However, to reflect real-world clinical needs (where comprehensive reporting is crucial), we penalize missing outputs to encourage participants to strive for complete predictions across all test cases.

In summary, while missing predictions are not outright disqualified, each missing result will directly reduce the final performance score. This approach balances flexibility for innovative methods with the practical necessity of generating results for all test cases in a clinical context.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking scheme was designed to ensure a fair and comprehensive evaluation of all submitted algorithms. By incorporating multiple metrics—such as ROUGE-L, BLEU-4, Scispacy Jaccard, and Embedding scores—the scheme assesses both the structural and semantic quality of the generated reports, prioritizing clinical relevance and accuracy. This multi-metric approach provides a balanced assessment, reflecting the diverse requirements of pathology report generation tasks. Furthermore, using the final submission for testing ensures that participants can iteratively refine their methods, promoting innovation and robustness while maintaining consistency in evaluation across all teams.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Not applicable.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Not applicable.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Not applicable.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A